

ANALYSIS OF TOOL WEAR DURING MACHINING METAL MATRIX COMPOSITES

S. Kannan¹, H. A. Kishawy¹, I. M. Deiab², M. K. Surappa³

¹*Dept. of Mechanical Engineering, University of New Brunswick, Canada*

²*Dept. of Mechanical Engineering, American University of Sharjah, U.A.E*

³*Dept. of Metallurgy, Indian Institute of Science, India*

SUMMARY: Machining of metal matrix composites (MMCs) has been notoriously difficult due to the extremely abrasive nature of the reinforcements and presents a significant challenge to the industry. This paper presents an analytical tool flank wear rate model that has been developed for orthogonal cutting processes. In this approach, the wear volume loss is formulated based on the process parameters and reinforcement properties. Then, the flank wear rate is developed by considering the tool geometry in orthogonal metal cutting. The developed model was validated with orthogonal cutting tests conducted on 6061 aluminium MMC reinforced with Al₂O₃ particulates of different mean sizes (9.5µm, 20µm, 25µm) and volume fractions (10% and 20%) under similar cutting conditions. The results showed good agreement between the predicted and measured flank wear data.

KEYWORDS: Cutting, Tool wear, MMC.

INTRODUCTION

Metal matrix composites (MMCs) have been widely used in the industries because of their superior properties over those of non-reinforced alloys [1, 2]. The properties of the composite depend upon the particular constituents and volume fraction used. Generally, reinforcing the matrix with fibers gives greatest improvement in mechanical properties. However such reinforcements have the drawback of exhibiting anisotropic properties and they are very costly to manufacture by the conventional mechanical processing [3]. The composites reinforced with particulates tend to offer improvements in properties and are more isotropic and can be processed by conventional methods [4]. The strengthening mechanisms of discontinuously reinforced aluminium matrix composites have been the subject of research [4-9]. The strengthening mechanisms in these materials have been categorized as, direct and indirect, depending on the characteristics of the matrix materials and the reinforcement particles as secondary phases [5]. Direct strengthening results from load transfer from the matrix to the reinforcement. Indirect strengthening results from the influence that the reinforcements may have on the matrix microstructure or deformation mode [5, 7]. In the composite system, there are many variables that can affect the strengthening results. These major variables that have been identified include matrix alloy, aging characteristics of the matrix, particle volume fraction and sizes.

STRENGTHENING MECHANISMS IN MMC

Generally, the mechanical behavior of MMC is affected by the presence of ceramic particulates that are dispersed in the aluminium matrix. It should also be noted here that the yielding behavior of the composite is largely dependent on the matrix properties. The yield stress of the matrix may, in fact, be higher than the matrix alloy. This is because of various

factors such as increased dislocation density and reduced grain size. Several authors [10 and references therein] have examined the various strengthening mechanisms that may be occurring in a particulate reinforced composite and have suggested that the strengthening due to the presence of the particulate is dependent on a variety of mechanisms. Solution heat treatment causes differential straining at the particle/matrix interface during quenching due to large difference in the coefficient of thermal expansion between the aluminium matrix and the ceramic reinforcement. This mechanism leads to plastic relaxation thus generating dislocations and numerous loops in the aluminium matrix. It is well known that dislocations act as precipitate nucleation sites during aging, and that the increased dislocation density promotes accelerated aging in matrix. Also, the matrix grain size is reduced by particles acting as nucleation sites during the solidification process. The grain size is also reduced by the formation of subgrains when dislocations are rearranged into boundaries within the grain [5, 11]. This results in a high dislocation density along the interfaces as the subgrains are formed in those grains. Contributions to material strengthening are also from particulates acting as barriers to the motion of dislocations. Recent investigations of the mechanical properties of aluminium MMCs have focused mainly on studying the contributions of the matrix towards strengthening of the composites.

MACHINABILITY STUDIES ON MMCs

Although the combination of a high strength ceramic reinforcement in a ductile aluminium matrix is exciting from the point of view of materials properties, significant research on solving numerous problems related to machining MMCs are yet to make major inroads. Considerable attention has been given to these materials due to high tool wear accrued during machining. The inherent abrasiveness of the hard reinforcement particles result in accelerated tool wear and premature tool failure. However, in view of the growing engineering applications of these materials, a need for detailed and systematic study of their machining characteristics is emphasized.

Nature of tool wear and wear mechanism

The addition of ceramic reinforcements increases the hardness and, consequently, the abrasion wear resistance of the metal matrix. MMC hardness is mainly dictated by the matrix-reinforcement combination, the form of reinforcement, the processing route used, and most importantly the reinforcement volume fraction and size. Machining plays an important role in the overall cost of manufacturing MMC components. Conventional machining processes have been used for a large variety of different MMC materials. Several investigators have agreed upon the fact that the extremely abrasive nature of MMCs makes the choice of tool material and operating parameters critical [12-18]. Published literature on the machinability of particulate MMCs indicated that, only diamond tools (PCD and CVD) provide a useful tool life, which is due to their higher hardness than the common reinforcements. Gindy et al. [19] tested several grades of WC tools as well as PCD when turning Zn-Al MMC reinforced with 15 vol% of SiC particulates. It was reported that some carbides lasted only for few seconds, irrespective of the cutting parameters, while other grades achieved significant values of tool life at low cutting speed, low depth of cut and even at high feed rates. From their investigation, the cutting speed has been identified as having most important effect on tool life. PCD was detailed as the best tool material to machine this particular MMC. Variety of cutting tool materials have been tested by several authors to machine MMCs reinforced with different combinations of reinforcements. It has been shown from these experiments that tool wear was very much dependent on the hardness of the reinforcement. Ceramic tools were found to be unsatisfactory, while, the cemented carbides were preferred when machining at low cutting speeds and high feed rates. Not surprisingly, the best performance was achieved

with PCD tools irrespective of the type of reinforcement. Component surface quality was shown to be strongly dependent on tool material and it was suggested that the reason why PCD gave best results was that it was able to cut the reinforcement [18, 20-23]. Hung et al. [13, 24] carried out comprehensive cutting experiments to study the machinability characteristics of MMCs. It was recommended that roughing with uncoated WC inserts and then finishing with PCD tool is the most economical way in machining silicon carbide-reinforced aluminium composites. Brun et al. [25] reported that the hardness ratio between the tool material and reinforcement particles played an important role for flank wear of the inserts made of homogenous materials.

When the rubbing surfaces are free from any active chemical environment, the mechanical wear process contributes the major share in the total wear volume particularly at low cutting speeds. Such mechanical wear takes place due to abrasion as result of ploughing into the softer matrix by hard constituents such as carbides, inclusions, etc. This is referred to as the two-body wear process. Abrasive wear can also arise in a somewhat different situation, when hard, abrasive particles are introduced between sliding surfaces and abrade material off each. The mechanism of this form of abrasive wear seems to be that an abrasive grain adheres temporarily to one of the sliding surfaces, or else is embedded in it, and plow out a groove in the other. This is referred to as the three-body wear process [26]. During cutting MMCs, the aforementioned two types of wear processes have been reported to occur [12, 27-29]. Two-body abrasive wear occurs when there is micro-cutting of the reinforcement particles on the tool surface [29]. Three-body abrasive wear occurs when the reinforcement particles that are debonded from the matrix during machining comes into contact with the tool surface. These loose particles get entrapped between the machined surface and the cutting tool surface causing severe abrasive wear.

Effect of matrix hardness

Both theory and experimental work by several authors indicated that the degree of strengthening imparted by the reinforcement increases with the matrix work hardening rate. The hardness and yield strength of the composite is changed by the heat treatment procedures. Composites aged to peak hardness have a higher volume fraction of strong precipitates which act as an obstacle to dislocation movement. This mechanism results in an increase in the dynamic shear stress of the composite during metal cutting. A strong correlation between matrix hardness and machinability of cast aluminium based composites was shown reported by Lane [30]. Cutting tests were carried out on silicon carbide particulate reinforced aluminium composites subjected to different heat treatment conditions. The results of the experimentation showed that naturally aged composites were more abrasive and higher tool wear was developed than the artificially aged samples. However, a similar study conducted on 6061 composite showed a reverse trend. The cutting tool wear is highly dependent on the work hardening properties of the matrix material. The results of investigations carried out by Tomac and Tonnessen [16] revealed that the thermal softening characteristics of the matrix at higher feed rates was a reason for improved tool life. They mentioned that the increase in feed rates improves the heat conduction from the cutting zone onto the workpiece thus softening the matrix material. The same result of decreased tool wear rate was obtained from the work of Finn and Srivatsava [31]. But they reasoned that at higher feed rates there's a reduction in contact between the hard ceramic particles and the cutting tool edge and hence lower tool wear.

Effect of reinforcement size and volume fraction

Several investigations were carried out to study the effect of particulate volume fraction and size on the progression of tool wear rate [28, 29, 32]. It has been shown that the particulate sizes together with the cutting speed has much stronger effect on tool wear rate than the volume fraction of particulates [33]. A critical volume fraction and finer reinforcing particles hold the key for a better tool life [28, 29, 33]. A relation between the densities of the reinforcement and matrix and the tool wear acceleration is also found to exist [29].

It's clearly evident from the literature that most studies on the machining characteristics of MMCs have been based entirely from experimental results. Furthermore, there's still no systematic approach to model the tool flank wear rate during machining metal matrix composites. Thus, the primary objective of this study is to conduct an investigation to understand the influence of various factors and their interactions on the progression of cutting tool wear during intermittent cutting of MMCs. Further, a methodology for analytical modeling of tool wear progression has been developed as a function of cutting tool/matrix/reinforcement material properties and process parameters in orthogonal metal cutting.

MODELING OF FLANK WEAR RATE

The study of physical processes taking place at the flank contact area is of at most importance in metal cutting. This study impacts the modeling of tool flank wear rate as well as the integrity of the machined surface. High normal and frictional stresses act at the tool/workpiece contact area. Based on the experimental observations of several authors it can be concluded that during machining MMCs, the flank wear of the cutting tool increases with increasing average normal stress acting along the tool flank face and the number of hard reinforcements impinging the cutting tool and decreases with increasing hardness of the cutting tool [16, 25, 31]. A strong correlation has been found to exist between the wear and energy spent during sliding contacts [34]. Considerable energy has to be spent during metal cutting in order to cause a purposeful fracture of the layer to be removed. This energy flows into the shear zone through the cutting tool, which is the continuously loaded component in the cutting system. The cutting tool material properties and geometry plays an important role in this energy transfer [35]. The wear rate of the cutting tool can be modeled based on the Holm-Archard formulation [36]. The cutting tool wear volume increases with an increase in energy consumed and decreases with increasing cutting tool hardness (H_t). Increases in energy consumed for machining results in an increase in cutting tool wear volume. The energy consumed for machining can be represented in terms of power (P_c) required by the cutting system as:

$$\left(\frac{V}{t}\right) = \left(\frac{K_w \beta P_c}{H_t}\right) \quad (1)$$

where, V is the wear volume, K_w is the proportionality constant which can be determined by a set of experimental results using minimum root mean square error method, t is machining time and β is an empirical constant related to properties of the ceramic particulate reinforcement and given by :

$$\left[\beta = \left(\frac{H_a}{H_t}\right) \left(\frac{D}{d}\right) \left(\frac{f_v}{\alpha(1-f_v)}\right)\right],$$

where, H_a is the reinforcement hardness, (D/d) is the average particulate diameter to inter-particulate spacing ratio, f_v is the volume fraction of particulates, $(1-f_v)$ is the volume fraction of the matrix and α is the Weibull probability of un-damaged ceramic particles (55% in this case). The Weibull probability has been calculated based on the model proposed by Kishawy et al. [37]. The power required by the cutting system, (P_c) , can be expressed as the product of energy per unit volume of metal removed (U_s) and metal removal rate (MRR), i.e.,

$$P_c = U_s * (b * h * v), \quad (2)$$

where, b is width of cut, h is undeformed chip thickness, v is the cutting speed. Substituting Eqn. 2 into Eqn. 1 and after a time dt , the wear volume along the flank face will be:

$$\left(\frac{dV}{dt}\right) = \left(\frac{K_W \beta}{H_t}\right) * (U_s b h v), \quad (3)$$

From the cutting tool geometry in Fig. 1, the volumetric wear rate can be written as [38]:

$$\left(\frac{dV}{dt}\right) = bVB \left(\frac{dVB}{dt}\right) \left(\frac{\tan \eta}{1 - \tan \eta \tan \gamma}\right) \quad (4)$$

where, η is clearance angle and γ is the rake angle. Based on the Eqns. 3 and 4, the flank wear rate during orthogonal machining of metal matrix composites can be expressed as:

$$bVB \left(\frac{dVB}{dt}\right) \left(\frac{\tan \eta}{1 - \tan \eta \tan \gamma}\right) = \left(\frac{K_W \beta}{H_t}\right) * (U_s b h v) \quad (5)$$

$$\left(\frac{dVB}{dt}\right) = \left(\frac{K_w \beta U_s h v}{VB H_t \left(\frac{\tan \eta}{1 - \tan \eta \tan \gamma}\right)} \right) \quad (6)$$

EXPERIMENTAL VALIDATION

The composite billets required for the experimentation were fabricated by liquid metallurgy route. Appropriate quantities of preheat treated alumina particles of 9.5 μ m, 20 μ m and 25 μ m sizes were dispersed into molten 6061 aluminium alloy by vortex technique. Composite melts were degassed with nitrogen gas and subsequently poured into 65mm diameter and 250mm length cylindrical cast iron moulds. 6061 aluminium MMCs reinforced with 10vol% and 20vol% of Al₂O₃ particles were fabricated and used for machining studies. The microstructures of the different particulate sized 6061/ 10vol% Al₂O₃ MMCs are shown in Fig. 2. Representative samples were taken from the different cast composite billets and the inter particle distance measurements were made using the grid technique. Orthogonal cutting tests were carried out at three different cutting speeds (160m/min, 222m/min, and 300m/min) and at constant feed of 0.1mm and width of cut of 3mm. Un-coated tungsten carbide cutting inserts with zero rake angle, 7° clearance angle and hardness of 17GPa were used in the experiments. In order to remove dirt, chips and most of the built-up edges before measuring tool wear, the cutting inserts were ultrasonically cleaned in 10% sodium hydroxide.

Fig. 1: Schematic representation of the tool flank wear volume

Fig. 2: Microstructures of 6061/10 vol% Al_2O_3 MMCs reinforced with different particulate sizes. (A) $9.5\mu m$; (B) $20\mu m$; (C) $25\mu m$

Flank wear was measured with a toolmaker's microscope with each tool being measured three times. The chips were collected after each cutting tests and the average value of deformed chip thickness was measured. The reinforcement properties used were: $H_a = 20GPa$ and $\alpha = 0.55$. With the known data on cutting tool geometry and material properties along with the constant K_w found using the minimum root mean square error method (calibrated using experimental data), the flank wear length (VB), for a given period of cutting can be determined using Eqn. 6.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The tool wear progression during cutting $9.5\mu m / 10 \text{ vol}\%$ MMC at three different cutting speeds are shown in Fig. 3 (a). As depicted in the graphs, the rate of wear progression was lower for this type of MMC when compared to other cases. The reason for lower tool wear is due to the finer reinforced particulate sizes. These sizes are comparable to the second phase precipitate particle sizes and hence had less drastic effect on the cutting tool wear. In addition, the volume fraction of the reinforcements was also low in this MMC. The flank wear rates predicted using the developed model was found to be well within the limits of divergence for all the cutting speeds considered. Fig. 3(b) shows the comparison of wear progression for the measured and predicted

cases during cutting $20\mu\text{m} / 10\text{vol}\%$ MMC. An increase in the mean particulate size resulted in a considerable increase in the wear rate when compared to the $9.5\mu\text{m} / 10\text{vol}\%$ MMC under similar cutting conditions. The spacing between the ceramic particulates plays an important role in the tool performance. This parameter was incorporated into the developed model. An increase in the particulate size results in an increased contact between the reinforcements and the cutting tool and hence severe tool wear. Fair agreement was found between the predicted and measured flank wear progression for all the three cutting speeds.

Fig. 3: Flank wear progression during cutting 6061MMC with different particulates sizes
(A) $v = 160\text{ m/min}$, (B) $v = 222\text{ m/min}$, (C) $v = 300\text{ m/min}$

Similar acceleration in flank wear was observed during cutting of $25\mu\text{m} / 10\text{vol}\%$ MMC at different cutting speeds as shown in Fig. 4. The progression of flank wear was still more pronounced during machining $25\mu\text{m} / 10\text{vol}\%$ MMC than the $20\mu\text{m} / 10\text{vol}\%$ MMC. Under the conditions of high speed machining, the properties of the matrix material plays an important role in the tool wear progression. Thermal softening characteristics of the matrix helps in reducing the cutting tool wear, whereas, the tendency of the matrix material to work harden leads to acceleration in the tool wear. Increases in the cutting velocity and mean particulate size causes the kinetic energy gained by the hard particles, that are usually harder than the carbide cutting tools used in this investigation. At higher velocities, the abrasive particles slide against the cutting tool flank face with their sharp active edges resulting in two-body abrasion.

Fig. 4: Flank wear progression during cutting $25\mu\text{m} / 10\text{vol}\%$ MMC at different cutting speeds
(A) $v = 160\text{ m/min}$, (B) $v = 222\text{ m/min}$, (C) $v = 300\text{ m/min}$

Due to the weak interface between the matrix and the reinforcement, the bonds are broken as a result of localized flow of the matrix and the stress exerted by the cutting tool. These particles which are free to roll are trapped between the cutting tool and the matrix. It should be noted here that the ability of the particles to roll and slide between the tool and the machined surface depends highly on the matrix material hardness which has been considered in this study. The effect of volume fraction on the progression of flank wear has been studied and this parameter has been incorporated into the developed model. The predicted and the measured wear progression for $20\mu\text{m} / 20\text{vol}\%$ MMC are depicted in Fig. 5. For a mean particle size of $20\mu\text{m}$, an increase in the volume fraction of the reinforcements resulted in an increase of flank wear for the similar cutting conditions considered as shown in Fig. 6. For the same particle sized MMC, the number of hard particles impacting and sliding along the flank face of the cutting tool increases with an increase in volume fraction. This increase in number of abrasive particles contacting the flank surface of the tool, results in rapid abrasion of the tool material causing severe tool nose rounding and flank wear.

Fig. 5: Flank wear progression during cutting $20\mu\text{m} / 20 \text{ vol}\%$ MMC ($v = 300 \text{ m/min}$)

Fig. 6: Comparison of tool flank wear during cutting 6061 / Al_2O_3 MMC reinforced with different volume fractions ($v = 300 \text{ m/min}$)

SUMMARY

A novel approach for predicting the wear rate during orthogonal machining of metal matrix composites is presented. The developed model for flank wear prediction is based on the power required for machining and takes into account of the material properties of the matrix and reinforcement particulates. The model also incorporates the cutting tool geometry in orthogonal machining. The model validated under different cutting speeds showed a fair agreement with the measured wear rate. The cutting tool wear was found to accelerate with the increase in average particle size and volume fraction with the former showing dominant effect on tool wear.

REFERENCES

- [1] Rohatgi, P., "Cast Aluminium Matrix Composites for Automotive Applications," *Journal of Organomet. Chem.*, (1991), pp. 10-15.
- [2] Dinwoodie, J., "Automotive Applications for MMC's based on Short Staple Alumina Fibres," *SAE Technical Paper Series, Int. Con. Exp.*, Detroit, Michigan, (1987), pp. 23-27.
- [3] Girot, F. A., J. M. Quenisset, R. Naslain, "Discontinuously Reinforced Al Matrix Composites", *Comput Sci Technol*, Vol. 30, (1987), pp.155-184.
- [4] Mcdanels, D. L., "Analysis of Stress Strain, Fracture and Ductility Behavior of Aluminium Matrix Composites Containing Discontinuous Silicon Carbide Reinforcement," *Metall Trans A*, Vol.16A, (1985), pp.1105-1115.
- [5] Gnjidic, Z., D. Bozic, and M. Mitkov, "The Influence of SiC Particles on the Compressive Properties of Metal Matrix Composites," *Materials Characterization*, Vol.47, (2001), pp.129-138.
- [6] Manoharan, M., and J. J. Lewandowski, "Crack Initiation and Growth Toughness of an Aluminium Metal Matrix Composite," *Acta Metall Mater*, Vol. 38, (1990), pp. 489-496.
- [7] Chawla, N., C. Andres, and J. W. Jones, "The Effect of Reinforcement Volume Fraction and Particle Size on the Fatigue Behavior of an Aluminium Alloy/SiC Composite," *Ind Heat*, Vol. 56, (1999), pp.61-66.
- [8] England, J., and I. W. Hall, "On the Effect of Strength of the Matrix in Metal Matrix Composites," *Scripta Metall*, Vol.20, (1986), pp.697-700.
- [9] Dai, L. H., Z. Ling, and Y. L. Bai, "A Strain Gradient Strengthening Law for Particle Reinforced Metal Matrix Composites," *Scripta Mater*, Vol. 41, (1999), pp.245-251.
- [10] Miller, W. S., and F. J. Humphreys, "Strengthening Mechanisms in Particulate Metal Matrix Composites," *Scripta Metallurgica et Materialia*, Vol. 25/1, (1991), pp.33-38.
- [11] Rees, D. W. A., "Deformation and Fracture of Metal Matrix Particulate Composites Under Combined Loading," *Composites*, Vol. 29A, (1998), pp.171-182.
- [12] Hung, N. P., F. Y. C.Boey, K. A. Khor, Y. S. Phua and H. F. Lee, "Machinability of Aluminium Alloys Reinforced With Silicon Carbide Particulates," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, Vol. 56, (1996), pp. 966-977.
- [13] Hung, N. P., V. C. Venkatesh and N. L. Loh, "Cutting Tools for Metal Matrix Composites," *Key Engineering Materials*, Vol. 138-140, (1998), pp. 289-325.
- [14] Songmene, V., M. Balazinski, "Machinability of Graphitic Metal Matrix Composites as a Function of Reinforcing Particles," *Annals of the CIRP*, Vol. 48/1, (1999), pp. 77-80.
- [15] Cronjager, L., and D. Meister, "Machining of Fibre and Particle Reinforced Aluminium," *Annals of the CIRP*, Vol. 41/1, (1992), pp. 63-66.
- [16] Tomac, N., and K. Tonnessen, "Machinability of Particulate Aluminium Matrix Composites," *Annals of the CIRP*, Vol. 41/1, (1992), pp. 55-58.
- [17] Weinert, K., "Consideration of Tool Wear Mechanism When Machining Metal Matrix Composites (MMC)," *Annals of the CIRP*, Vol. 42/1, (1993), pp. 95-98.
- [18] Monaghan, J., and P. O'Reilly, "Machinability of Al Alloy/SiC Metal Matrix Composite," *Process. Adv. Mater.*, Vol. 2, (1992), pp. 37-46.
- [19] Gindy, N. N., and A. J. Clegg, "Machining Metal Matrix Composites," *Proc. of the BNF 7th International Conference-The Materials Revolution Through 90's*, V32, (1989).
- [20] Looney, L. A., J. M. Monaghan, and P. O'Reilly, "The Turning of an Al/SiC Metal Composite," *Journal of Material Processing Technology*, Vol. 33, (1992), pp. 453-468.

- [21] Chambers, A. R., and S. E. Stephens, "Machining of Al-5 Mg Reinforced with 5 vol% Saffil and 15 vol% SiC Fibres," *Journal of Material Science and Engineering*, Vol. A135, (1990), pp. 287-290.
- [22] Yanming, Q., and Z. Zehna, "Tool Wear and its Mechanism for Cutting SiC Reinforced Al Matrix Composites," *Journal of Material Processing Technology*, Vol. 100, (2000), pp. 194-199.
- [23] Lin, J. T., D. Bhattacharya, and C. Lane, "Machinability of a Silicon Carbide Reinforced Aluminium Metal Matrix Composite," *Wear*, Vol. 181, (1995), pp. 883-888.
- [24] Hung, N. P., F. Y. C. Boey, K. A. Khor, C. A. Oh and H. F. Lee, "Machinability of Cast and Powder Formed Aluminium Alloys Reinforced With SiC Particles," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, Vol. 48, (1995), pp. 291-297.
- [25] Brun, M. K., M. Lee, and F. Gorsler, "Wear Characteristics of Various Hard Materials for Machining SiC reinforced Aluminium Alloy," *Wear*, Vol. 104, (1985), pp. 21-29.
- [26] Burwell, J. T., "Survey of Possible Wear Mechanisms," *Wear*, Vol.1, (1957), pp. 119-141.
- [27] Lane, C. T., "Machining Characteristics of Particle-Reinforced Aluminium," *Proceedings of the Conference Fabrication of Particulate Reinforced Metal Matrix Composites*, September 17-19, (1990), Montreal, Canada.
- [28] Ibrahim, C., M. Turker, and U. Seker, "Evaluation of Tool Wear When Machining SiC Reinforced Al-2014 Alloy Matrix Composites," *Materials and Design*, Vol. 25, (2004), pp. 251-255.
- [29] Xiaoping, L., and W. K. H. Seah, "Tool Wear Acceleration in Relation to Workpiece Reinforcement Percentage in Cutting of Metal Matrix Composites," *Wear*, Vol. 247, (2001), pp. 161-171.
- [30] Lane, C.T., "Drilling and Tapping of SiC Reinforced Al," *Proceedings of the Machining of Composite Materials Conference*, (1993), ASM International, Pittsburgh, PA.
- [31] Finn, M., and A. Srivatsava, "Machining of Advanced and Engineered Materials," *Proceedings of the CSME Symposium*, McMaster University, (1996), pp. 616-623.
- [32] Sahin, M., M. Kok, and H.Celik, "Tool Wear and Surface Roughness of Alumina Particle Reinforced Aluminium Alloy Composites," *Journal of Materials Processing Technology*, Vol. 128, (2002), pp. 280-291.
- [33] Lane, C., and M. Finn, "Observations on Using CVD Diamond in Milling MMCs," *Proceedings of the Symposium on Materials Issues in Machining and the Physics of the Machining Processes*, (1992), TMS, Chicago, IL.
- [34] Huq, M. Z. and J. P. Celis, "Expressing Wear Rate in Sliding Contacts Based on Dissipated Energy," *Wear*, Vol. 252, (2002), pp. 375-383.
- [35] Komarovskiy, A. A., and V. P. Astakhov, "Physics of Strength and Fracture Control: Fundamentals of the Adaptation of Engineering Materials and Structures," CRC Press, Boca – Raton, (2002).
- [36] Rabinowicz, E., *Friction and Wear of Materials*, Wiley Interscience, Second Edition, (1995), pp. 169-170.
- [37] Kishawy, H. A., S. Kannan, and M. Balazinski, "An Energy Based Force Model for Orthogonal Cutting of Metal Matrix Composites," *Annals of the CIRP*, Vol. 53, (2004), pp. 91-94.
- [38] Bhattacharyya, A., and A. B. Chattopadhyay, "Investigation of Flank Wear Growth by Employing a Stochastic Model," *12th Congress of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics*, IIT, Delhi, (1967), pp. 181-192.